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Brazilian Jiu-Jitsu and Grappling in Law Enforcement Training: Impacts on the Tactical Performance of the AT.-P.I. Unit of the Italian Guardia di Finanza

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ABSTRACT

Brazilian Jiu-Jitsu (BJJ) and Grappling are combat disciplines emphasizing takedowns, ground control, immobilization, and submission through dominant positional strategies, without strikes. Their technical principles focus on efficiency, precision, and the exploitation of an opponent's force, making them highly relevant for law enforcement contexts that require graduated, controlled, and non-violent use of force. This study investigates the physiological and performance responses of specialized police trainees during a simulated use-of-force scenario and examines the potential benefits of integrating BJJ and Grappling into training programs. Thirty cadet officers of the Italian Guardia di Finanza of the speciality “Antiterrorismo e Pronto Impiego”, who received a use-of-force and personal defense training, which included techniques and tactics of BJJ and Grappling, participated in a longitudinal assessment. Measurements included heart rate, maximal isometric handgrip strength, RPE, task completion time, and general physical fitness parameters. Heart rate increased significantly from pre- to post-simulation ($p < 0.001$), indicating high cardiovascular response. The statistically significant reduction in grip strength after the simulation in both the dominant hand ($p < 0.001$) and the non-dominant hand ($p < 0.002$), reflected acute neuromuscular activation and fatigue. The mean simulation completion time was $11'54'' \pm 10'06''$, with a Borg CR-10 perceived exertion score of 7 ± 2 . Physical fitness assessments showed mean VO_2max of $52 \pm 3 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, 13 ± 3 pull-ups, 63 ± 13 push-ups, and 116 ± 49 sit-ups. These findings demonstrate the substantial physiological demands of use-of-force situations and support the inclusion of BJJ and Grappling in law enforcement training to enhance operational efficiency, controlled subject management, and minimize injury risk.

Key Words: Brazilian Jiu-Jitsu; Grappling; Guardia di Finanza; Antiterrorismo e Pronto Impiego; law enforcement training; use-of-force simulation; tactical performance.

INTRODUCTION

In Italy, assaults against law enforcement officers are steadily increasing, from 2,655 cases in 2021 to 2,695 in 2024, averaging more than 7 assaults per day (Osservatorio ASAPS, 2025). This results in more injuries for both officers and perpetrators, and a rise in offences committed by officers themselves during the use of force. The current socio-legal context, marked by stricter jurisprudence and the widespread use of audio and video recordings that often lack full context, compels officers to exercise force flawlessly. Consequently, the training needs of Law enforcement agencies are increasing precisely in response to these renewed contexts.

The high efficiency of Brazilian Jiu-Jitsu (BJJ) and Grappling in both sports and self-defense suggests that their application within police activities could be a crucial factor in changing the future landscape of professional training for law enforcement in Italy.

Numerous studies have shown that the type, amount, and approach of the training received by officers influence their behavior in the field (Heusler and Sutter, 2022; Krätzig et al., 2021; Torres, 2018). From this, one can deduce how and to what extent training can affect the conduct of officers on duty, and therefore the importance of implementing innovative training programs that are consistent with operational use.

The main challenge for law enforcement officers is handling uncooperative or aggressive individuals during duties such as territorial control, roadside checks, combating illicit trafficking, or responding to emergencies. Standard-issue coercive tools (batons, TASERS, pepper spray, firearms) are often disproportionate, making mastery of unarmed skills essential for applying force correctly, safely, effectively, legally, and for the officer's personal defence.

Furthermore, considering that the most suitable safety position for managing resistance is on the ground, and that, as some statistics indicate, in approximately 60% of use-of-force situations, it is the subject who forces the officers to the ground (ASLET, 1997; Calibre Press, 2003), it is therefore essential to address the issue of improving officer effectiveness precisely in the ground phases, the ideal context for the application of BJJ and Grappling.

Studies in the literature regarding the effectiveness of BJJ in law enforcement activities are not numerous. A 2021 study highlighted how jiu-jitsu training for 95 officers in a Georgia State Police Department (U.S.A.) led to a 48% reduction in the injury rate for the entire Department, 53% fewer serious injuries to subjects on the receiving end of force, 59% less likelihood of encountering use-of-force situations, and 27% less use of TASERS compared to untrained officers (The Marietta Police Department, 2021). A study conducted on 30 officers of a Police Regiment in the city of Kryvyi Rih (Ukraine), who underwent specific training based on typical jiu-jitsu techniques and tactics, demonstrated a 17% reduction in TASER use, a 35% reduction in officer injuries, an 18% reduction in pepper spray use, and a 40% reduction in injuries among detainees (Hinzburh, 2023). A 2021 study examined 2,845 use-of-force cases by officers in a Minnesota State Police Department (U.S.A.) between 2014 and 2020 and found a 37% reduction in the use of force by officers, 44% fewer injuries to subjects on the receiving end of force, and 39% less TASER use after introducing BJJ techniques and tactics into officer training (Gottfried, 2021). Another 2024 study examined how the impact of Gracie Survival Tactics, a BJJ and grappling-based training seminar for police officers, seemed to have a

positive impact on officers' perception of the use of force, increasing self-esteem, providing awareness of new use-of-force options, and improving attitudes towards using less force (Luker, 2024).

There are other studies that have evaluated the effects of introducing other disciplines or combat sports related to BJJ and Grappling, such as Olympic Wrestling (Öztürk, 2023) and Judo (Jozić et al., 2023), into the training of law enforcement and military forces with policing duties. However, these studies are focused more on the qualitative assessment of acquired skills, such as the execution of specific techniques characteristic of the respective disciplines.

Other studies have highlighted the physical and psychological impact of BJJ training, particularly on the officer's confidence in facing a physical confrontation (Andreato et al., 2017; Harmon, 2022; Willing et al., 2019) and have found additional positive benefits of BJJ training on decision-making and focus, both of which can be linked to confidence during the management of a use-of-force situation (Sipe, 2024).

Another recent study has confirmed the positive benefits of BJJ training perceived on physical performance, conflict management, and confidence by police officers (Butler & Wang, 2024).

There are no studies on the topic in Italy. International research, however, shows positive effects of BJJ on officers' operational experiences, based on incident reports, questionnaires, and testimonies from use-of-force situations. These studies do not examine how BJJ training might affect physiological parameters, work efficiency, or performance metrics, and they were conducted in countries with legal and socio-political contexts very different from Italy.

Since real-life use-of-force situations cannot be measured directly, simulations during training can replicate these events realistically and in a standardized way. This allows for reliable analysis of performance parameters, focusing on the dynamics most common in law enforcement interventions, and provides a basis for future improvements.

The longitudinal study aims to measure physical, physiological, and performance parameters of officers during simulations of controlling a non-cooperative subject using BJJ and Grappling techniques. The goal is to guide future research on the effects of integrating these disciplines into law enforcement training and to develop a performance model for their use.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Partecipants

The participants were 30 male military personnel in training for the Anti-Terrorismo e Pronto Impiego (AT.-P.I.) specialty of the Guardia di Finanza in Orvieto. They were of the same body weight ($75 \text{ kg} \pm 5 \text{ kg}$), with an average age of 22, and had completed an 8-month training phase. During this phase, they received training in the use of force and personal defence, which included immobilisation and control techniques implemented using technical and tactical elements of BJJ and Grappling.

The AT.-P.I. specialty of the Guardia di Finanza represents a branch of the Corps with high-level operational tasks, including maintaining public order and security, protecting at-risk individuals, territorial control, and surveillance of sensitive targets. These tasks make the personnel of this branch highly exposed to use-of-force situations, including significant ones.

Procedures

The data collection was conducted before and after a use-of-force immobilisation and control simulation. For completeness, physical parameters regarding general fitness were also assessed using some of the most commonly employed tests for evaluating security and emergency response personnel.

The simulation involved one of the most recurring scenarios that can occur during a typical territorial patrol and control service: namely, when a patrol composed of two officers must immobilise and control a subject offering a certain degree of resistance. The choice to use two officers to perform the immobilisation instead of a single officer was made for two reasons:

1. although there are no studies establishing the impossibility of a single officer immobilising a resisting subject, the operational practices of law enforcement agencies tend to favour the intervention of multiple officers to ensure the safety and effectiveness of the operation;
2. based on direct experience of the author gained in the specific field (both in training and operational contexts), it can be established that a single officer, on average, cannot control and immobilise a subject of average build who is offering even moderate active resistance, especially if the immobilisation is to be completed using handcuffs;

In order to make the simulation as realistic and reliable as possible, while simultaneously safeguarding the safety and health of the participants and the uke (training partners), the use of any form of striking was prohibited for all subjects involved in the simulation.

The officers, i.e., the participants, all had the same body weight (± 5 kg), identified within a range of 70 to 80 kg. This choice reflects the researchers' intention to make the simulation more realistic by standardising the weight of the officers comprising the patrol. This was done for two reasons: first, to identify an average physique that could approximately represent that of law enforcement officers in Italy, and second, because weight in these contexts—which are comparable in performance models to combat sports—represents a significant element influencing performance (Di Felice & Manno, 2010, p. 18-19; Baribeau et al., 2022).

The subjects to be immobilised (uke), selected from other military personnel in training, also all had the same weight (± 5 kg), identified within a range of 80 to 90 kg. This was done to ensure the same degree of difficulty for all participants in the simulation. The choice to select uke who were heavier than the two officers in the patrol was adopted because, although it is impossible to define—even approximately—a standard physique that could identify the typical subject who normally offers this type of resistance to Law enforcement, the researchers still wanted to add a moderate additional challenge for the officers to make the simulation more realistic (the probability of facing subjects who are even much heavier is always high in operational service). However, this was done without making the simulation excessively long or difficult to complete.

The simulation ended when the two officers successfully placed the subject in a prone position with their arms positioned behind their back and their wrists secured together with handcuffs, without the use of any form of striking.

The subject offering resistance, meanwhile, aimed to consistently exert the same intensity of physical resistance, basing their conduct solely on two activities:

1. trying to avoid being forced into a prone position by the officers;
2. if on the ground, trying to avoid being immobilised.

They were not permitted to attempt any escape nor to use any form of striking.

A total of 15 simulations were conducted, involving 15 patrols of 2 officers each and 10 uke, one per simulation.

Measures

The parameters related to performance in the use-of-force context that were measured are both quantitative and qualitative.

The following were measured before the simulation:

1. heart rate (HR) of the two officers;
2. maximum isometric grip strength (handgrip) performed with the dominant (D) and non-dominant (ND) hand.

The following were measured after the simulation:

1. the time taken to complete the simulation;
2. heart rate (HR) of the two officers;
3. maximum isometric grip strength (handgrip) performed with the dominant (D) and non-dominant (ND) hand;
4. the Rate of Perceived Exertion (RPE) using the Borg scale.

The HR of the two officers was measured using carotid palpation, placing the first and second fingers on the carotid artery near the larynx (ACSM, 2010, p. 80). This method is recognized in the literature for measuring HR in the context of physically demanding combat sports, by dividing the time taken to measure 30 beats and multiplying this value by 60 (Cazorla et al., 1984). Maximum isometric handgrip strength was assessed using the handgrip strength test (Cronin et al., 2017), with a digital GripX dynamometer (198 lbs / 90 kg). The test was performed both before and after the immobilisation simulation, using both the strong and weak hand. To estimate the rate of perceived exertion (RPE) post-simulation, the Borg CR-10 scale from 0 to 10 was used (Borg, 1998).

To assess the general fitness of the participants, the Body Mass Index (BMI) was used to define the weight/height ratio, along with the Cooper Test and tests for the maximum number of consecutive repetitions of pull-ups, push-ups, and sit-ups.

For time measurement in heart rate calculation, two Faviye XL-013 stopwatches were used. For measuring the time taken to complete the simulation and for the Cooper Test, a Binloo XL-009A stopwatch was used.

The data are presented as mean and standard deviation (\pm SD), accompanied by relevant charts, and describe:

1. execution time of an immobilisation and control simulation on a subject weighing 85 kg (\pm 5 kg);
2. HR before and after an immobilisation and control simulation on a subject weighing 85 kg (\pm 5 kg);
3. results of handgrip test performed with the dominant and non-dominant hand before and after the simulation;

4. Rate of perceived exertion (RPE) using the Borg scale;
5. BMI (Body Mass Index);
6. Cooper Test: distance covered in a maximum time of 12 minutes;
7. pull-up test;
8. push-up test;
9. sit-up test.

The distribution of the data will not be tested because the participants all had the same body weight (± 5 kg), had all undergone the same type of training, and had no personal experience in combat sports. Consequently, a normal distribution of the data is assumed.

Results

Table 1 presents the average of some anthropometric values of the participants and their BMI. Table 2 presents the general fitness values of the participants, obtained from the physical efficiency tests listed in the table.

Figure 1 presents the graph related to the completion times of the immobilization and control simulation, which have an average of 11 minutes 54 seconds \pm 10 minutes 06 seconds.

The data from the Borg scale show an average of 7.10 ± 1.95 points, where 0 represents complete rest and 10 represents maximum exertion.

Table 1 – Age and anthropometric characteristics of participants. Data presented as M (\pm SD)

	M=30
Age (year)	22 ± 1
Weight (kg)	75 ± 3
Height (cm)	$1,75 \pm 0,04$
BMI (kg*m⁻²)	24 ± 1

Table 2 –Physical parameters measured during physical fitness tests and BMI calculation. Data presented as M (\pm SD)

Variables	M=30
BMI	24
VO2max (ml·kg ⁻¹ ·min ⁻¹)	52 ± 3
pull-up (nr.)	13 ± 3
push-up (nr.)	63 ± 13
sit up (nr.)	116 ± 49

Figure 1 – Graph related to the simulation completion times

Figure 2 shows the graph related to the officers' HR in the pre- and post-intervention phases, with mean values of 74 ± 12 BPM in the pre-simulation phase and 143 ± 27 BPM

immediately after the simulation, highlighting a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$). Figures 3 and 4 show the results of the handgrip test before and after the intervention, with mean values of 50 ± 7 kg and 44 ± 8 kg in the dominant hand pre- and post-intervention respectively, and 46 ± 5 kg and 44 ± 8 kg in the non-dominant hand pre- and post-intervention, highlighting a statistically significant difference in both the dominant hand ($p < 0.001$) and the non-dominant hand ($p < 0.002$).

Figure 2 – Graph related to the difference between the mean HR recorded in the pre- and post-simulation phases.

Figure 3 – Graph related to the difference between the mean handgrip test results of the dominant hand pre- and post-simulation.

Figure 4 – Graph related to the difference between the mean handgrip test results of the non-dominant hand pre- and post-simulation.

Discussion

Heart rate is widely recognized as a reliable indicator of exercise intensity (McArdle et al., 2018, Chapter 21; Wilmore & Costill, 2005, pp. 255-256; Karvonen & Vuorimaa, 1988). Therefore, the statistically significant difference between resting heart rate and the heart rate recorded at the end of the simulation suggests a considerable increase in fatigue induced by this immobilisation and control activity of a non-cooperative subject during police operations.

Similarly, the post-simulation heart rate value can clearly represent an indicator of the effort intensity of this specific performance model. Therefore, an average heart rate of 143 BPM during use-of-force simulations may indicate a moderate level of exercise intensity, considering the subjects' average age (ACSM, 2017, p. 230). However, the standard deviation (27 BPM) still suggests significant fluctuations, which could indicate variations in activity intensity, as this is an effort that alternates periods of intermittent and intense exertion (as in combat sports),

interspersed with less intense phases and changes in pace. Furthermore, it should be noted that the average post-simulation heart rate accounts for both trials completed in shorter times and those completed in longer times. Consequently, the trial intensity was influenced by several variables, such as the physical conditioning of the subjects involved, the activity and technique of the uke, the level of intervention and participation in the action by both members of the patrol, and the duration of any static moments.

The average increase from 73 BPM to 143 BPM indicates a marked cardiovascular response, suggesting that the specific activity involved both physiological and psychological components. This increase may also be consistent with a certain activation of the sympathetic nervous system, which prepares the body for action by increasing heart rate, blood pressure, and the release of catecholamines. Considering that the simulation involves non-stereotypical combat scenarios or situations of perceived threat, the increase in heart rate can be influenced not only by physical exertion but also by psychological stress, thereby increasing fatigue and reducing performance (Grossman, 2008, Chapter 1). In this regard, it could be useful in future studies to assess heart rate after a specific recovery period, as a rapid return to baseline values indicates a good level of cardiovascular fitness, while a slow recovery might suggest high fatigue or stress. This could inform potential adjustments to the training program, especially regarding cardiovascular endurance (aerobic capacity and VO₂max), since greater aerobic capacity and power enable sustaining high-intensity action, delaying the onset of fatigue and allowing for rapid recovery during lull phases, consequently enhancing officer performance.

Handgrip strength is a predictive indicator of overall body strength and muscular endurance, with significant implications in health, occupational, and security fields (Vaishya et al., 2024). In the occupational context, handgrip strength reflects the muscular capacity of the upper limbs and overall physical strength (Zaccagni et al., 2020). Furthermore, grip strength is an objective index of the functional integrity of the upper limb and is assessed through dynamometry, as it is an economical, fast, and easy-to-use technique that also helps detect the loss of physiological muscle function (Rojas et al., 2012). The handgrip test using dynamometers is also highly specific for evaluating maximum isometric handgrip strength, particularly in sports where handgrip strongly influences performance, including BJJ (Kons et al., 2020). In this case, the statistically significant difference in the average strength parameters between pre- and post-simulation, both for the dominant hand (-12%) and the non-dominant hand (-6.5%), may indicate not only an evident overall reduction in grip strength but also a greater strength reduction in the strong hand (-12%) compared to the weak hand (-6.5%). This certainly points to an intense muscular effort that has measurably altered the officers' muscle performance, resulting in more pronounced fatigue. The intensive use of the upper limbs, especially the hands, has undoubtedly caused a reduction in muscle contraction capacity, similar to what occurs in physically dominant combat sports like BJJ. Some studies have documented strength losses of up to 20% in handgrip tests before and after matches (Franchini et al., 2003, 2005; Fernandez et al., 2008; Bonitch-Góngora et al., 2012; Kraemer et al., 2001). This demonstrates that the simulations in this longitudinal study represent activities with performance models comparable to those of BJJ and Grappling. This is because, whether for controlling an opponent or securing a resisting subject, a firm grip can make the difference in maintaining effective control without the need to resort to excessive force.

In the specific context of law enforcement, a 2019 systematic review that included 59 studies conducted on police officers from various countries, including the United States, Canada, Brazil, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Finland, Serbia, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Turkey, showed average maximum isometric handgrip strength parameters ranging from 24.1 to 65.3 kg (average of the mean values = 52.6 kg) (Marins et al., 2019). The average recorded in this study is 50 kg for the dominant hand and 46 kg for the non-dominant hand in male officers, suggesting that these standards are generally in line with those of other law enforcement officers.

The post-simulation reduction in grip strength undoubtedly highlights that in these situations, officers experience significant muscle fatigue. This can affect their ability to handle equipment, weapons, or execute control manoeuvres after a prolonged physical confrontation.

Therefore, it is necessary to consider future perspectives for improvement in the training domain through specific training protocols.

The average completion time for the immobilisation and control simulation (11'54") showed a very high standard deviation relative to the mean (SD = 10'06"). This indicates that the completion times for individual simulations vary significantly, with results ranging from 4 to 6 minutes, to 10-15 minutes, and even peaks of 30 to 40 minutes. The high variability does not appear to be due to individual differences in preparation (the sample received the same amount of training hours and had no prior specific individual technical background), but rather to the highly situational nature of the simulation itself. Unlike repetitive and standardised tasks, the use of force in an operational context is highly situational, influenced by strategies, the uke's level of resistance, the environment, and tactical decisions made in real-time. This also occurs in combat sports, where the time to finish techniques varies drastically based on the specific conditions that arise during the fight. Even among athletes of the same technical level, the time to execute a takedown or a submission can vary from a few seconds to several minutes, depending on the opponent's technical level and resistance, tactical opportunities, and unforeseen reactions. Similarly, in an immobilisation and control simulation, the specific conditions of the situation determine the execution time more than technical competency alone.

From a perspective of future studies, one could aim to reduce this variability by evaluating the use of more controlled and repeatable scenarios. While useful for more accurately measuring specific parameters, this would, however, come at the expense of the realistic component, as variability is a faithful reflection of the operational complexity that law enforcement officers face in reality.

The Borg Scale was used to measure perceived exertion during the simulation. It involves a self-assessment of effort intensity without the need for direct measurement tools, allowing for the correlation of subjective sensations with physiological parameters like heart rate. This tool has proven effective in various physically dominant combat sports, including Judo and BJJ, due to its practicality and convenience (Andreato et al., 2015; Del Vecchio et al., 2018). Considering that for this study the alternative version to the Borg 6-20 Scale, the CR-10 scale, was adopted, the average score of 7 ± 2 indicates that the perceived exertion was very intense, close to the maximum capacity of the officers, with qualitative descriptions from the scale being "very hard" or "very strenuous." An average value of 7 on the CR-10 scale is generally associated with an intensity corresponding to approximately 85-90% of maximum heart rate or high blood lactate levels. This can confirm that the simulation, despite showing an

average heart rate associated with moderate-intensity activity, required a strong physical and psychological commitment and may have induced neuromuscular and mental fatigue. Consequently, a real use-of-force situation could likely be characterized by an even more pronounced psychophysical exertion.

However, the high levels of stress caused by intense physical activity can alter the perception of exertion, leading some officers to deplete their resources faster than anticipated. Although the Borg scale is useful for monitoring this phenomenon, it remains a subjective measure that could be influenced by individual psychological factors.

Another aim of this study is to investigate and describe the parameters that measure the physical fitness of these officers. As previously mentioned, various tests were used to evaluate the participants.

The Body Mass Index (BMI) was used to estimate body condition. According to this index, individuals with a BMI between 18.5 and 24.9 are considered normal weight, those with a BMI of 25 to 29.9 are overweight, those with a BMI of 30 and above are obese, and those below 18.5 are underweight (Nuttall, 2015). The average BMI recorded shows that, although the mean and standard deviation of 24 ± 4 indicate that the officers' values are distributed approximately between 20 (normal weight) and 28 (moderate overweight), most officers are in a physical condition generally adequate for service. The mean suggests that some officers might be overweight (BMI > 25), while others could be at the lower end of normal weight or even tending towards underweight. However, BMI does not distinguish between muscle mass and body fat. Well-trained officers might have higher BMIs (>25) without being overweight due to greater muscle mass, while a low value (<20) could indicate low muscle mass, potentially disadvantageous for the operational demands of law enforcement. The prevalence of overweight and obesity among tactical populations (defence and security sectors) is estimated at 70-75%, which can negatively impact health and performance. A high BMI is positively associated with risk factors for cardiovascular diseases, metabolic diseases, and is often indicative of reduced performance and increased injury risk in general (Sergi, 2023). Nonetheless, BMI alone is insufficient to determine physical fitness. Future studies would benefit from incorporating other body composition tests, such as bioelectrical impedance analysis and skinfold measurements, or other anthropometric measurements (Jitnarin, 2014).

Police activity is considered high-risk due to its characteristic dangerous, stressful, and physically demanding situations. The risks officers face includes civil unrest, physical violence incidents, accidents, robberies, and armed confrontations. For this reason, professionals must possess effectiveness and precision in task execution, along with various physical abilities (such as muscular strength and endurance, cardiorespiratory capacity, power, speed, and agility). These elements are essential for performing duties with quality, even under intense physical and mental pressure. Furthermore, the importance of officers maintaining good physical condition is emphasized, as poor motor efficiency reduces performance and jeopardizes individual and collective safety. However, numerous pieces of evidence show that the fitness level of officers is often below the recommended standards for general health.

A further factor affecting police officer performance is the load from the personal protective equipment worn during duty, such as bulletproof vests, sidearms, and long guns. Previous studies have highlighted how the use of this mandatory equipment increases physiological demands on public safety officers. Consequently, a high level of fitness is

essential to undertake and complete complex tactical operations, such as dragging victims, transporting heavy loads, controlling aggressive suspects, and other similar tasks. Furthermore, the literature emphasizes the importance of maintaining high levels of physical fitness for the health benefits as well. In this regard, it has been demonstrated that individuals with greater cardiorespiratory capacity and strength have, respectively, a 57% and 45% lower risk of all-cause mortality (Marins et al., 2019).

For the assessment of aerobic power (VO_2max) and cardiovascular endurance, this study employed the Cooper Test, which remains widely recognized for identifying the fitness level of military personnel (Cooper, 2018; NSCA, 2017, pp.136-155). The 12-minute Cooper running test for the predictive evaluation of VO_2max requires running as many meters as possible within a 12-minute time limit, on a standard 400-meter track. VO_2max was then calculated using the equation $\text{VO}_2\text{max} = (\text{distance in meters} - 504.9)/44.73$ (Cooper, 1968). The results showed a mean and standard deviation of 2844 ± 131 meters covered in the test and a mean VO_2max value of $52 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

In the review by Marins et al. (2019), the mean values for the Cooper Test ranged from 2,298 to 2,353 m (average of the means = 2,326 m), with corresponding calculated mean VO_2max values of $44.8 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. This clearly demonstrates that the participants in this study show an average in both the distance covered in the specific test and the mean VO_2max values that exceed international standards.

Regarding muscular endurance, measurements primarily focused on the trunk and upper limbs. The test for the maximum number of consecutive pull-ups (without interruption) is, in the context of evaluating security and emergency response personnel, an excellent tool for assessing the pulling muscle strength of the upper limbs (NSCA, 2017, pp.136-155). In this study, the mean and standard deviation of the number of repetitions performed by the officers was 13 ± 3 . Compared to the average repetitions measured in various sector-specific studies, these results significantly exceed those parameters, which were between 4.8 and 12.1 repetitions (average of the means = 8.2 repetitions) (Marins, 2019).

The test for the maximum number of consecutive push-ups, performed without interruption, was used to assess the endurance of the pushing muscles of the upper limbs (NSCA, 2017, pp.136-155; ACSM, 2010, p. 93). It showed a mean and standard deviation of 63 ± 13 repetitions.

The test for the maximum number of consecutive sit-ups, performed without interruption, was used to assess the strength of the trunk stabilizer muscles (NSCA, 2017, pp.136-155; ACSM, 2010, p. 93). It showed a mean and standard deviation of 116 ± 49 repetitions.

It seems difficult to compare these last two parameters with those found in the specific literature, as scientific studies primarily present the test of the maximum number of push-ups and sit-ups performed within 60 seconds. In contrast, the tests conducted by the participants in this study are both tests that involve performing the maximum number of repetitions without time constraints, in line with the provisions for physical fitness evaluations within the training curriculum for these officers.

Based on the above, the demands and responses of this specific performance model place this physical activity squarely among high-intensity activities. It is characterized by

continuous and unforeseen pace variations, high muscular and cardiovascular demands, and significant cognitive engagement.

Limitations

The study highlights different limitations: individual variability in stress management, the difficulty of simulations in fully reproducing real operational conditions, and the effect of a controlled setting on emotional activation. Although realistic, collaboration between two operators may bias the data due to uneven physical involvement. In addition, physical tests administered immediately after the simulation may mainly reflect acute fatigue, making it useful to also assess recovery over time.

To improve result quality, future research should expand the sample size, further standardize simulations, include control groups, implement specific training protocols, and use more objective physiological measures. Despite these limitations, the study represents an innovative contribution, providing valuable insights into the effectiveness of BJJ and Grappling in law enforcement training and their potential role in optimizing operational preparedness under high-stress conditions.

Conclusions

The longitudinal study monitored officers' physical and physiological responses during training and high-stress use-of-force simulations, focusing on BJJ and Grappling techniques. By integrating physiological (heart rate), neuromuscular (handgrip), perceptual (Borg scale), operational (simulation time), and general fitness measures, it provides a multidimensional assessment of performance. Its realistic operational context ensures strong practical relevance, offering insights for optimizing law enforcement training under high-stress conditions.

The use of force during the execution of law enforcement duties represents an unfortunately ever more current necessity, characterized by numerous facets. The complex socio-political realities affecting all countries in the world today demand a rational, precise, and scientific approach to this subject.

It is essential to study this topic in a structured, multidisciplinary way, examining physiological, cognitive, and conditioning responses (such as stress, emotion management, neurophysiological reactions, and rapid decision-making) during use-of-force situations. From a training perspective, understanding these demands allows for targeted programs that combine physical conditioning and cognitive skills, while drawing from martial arts and combat sports to select techniques and tactics that ensure effective, proportionate, and rights-respecting interventions.

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